

SYNTHESIS OF HYDROGELS BASED ON COPOLYMERS OF CYCLOPROPANE-CONTAINING ALLYL ETHERS WITH MALEIC ANHYDRIDE, CROSS-LINKED WITH POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728577>

Abstract

The allyl ethers with ester and geminal chlorine substituents are synthesized in a three-membered cycle. By radical copolymerization of these ethers with maleic anhydride, the linear copolymers of alternating structure are obtained. As a result of chemical cross-linking of copolymers of polyethylene glycol with a molecular weight of 300 Da, the transparent elastic hydrogels differing with high adhesion to a glass substrate are obtained. The influence of the structure of cross-linked copolymers on their ability to swell in an aqueous medium is investigated. The parameters of the hydrogel mesh are studied. The possibility of using them as carriers of physiologically active compounds is investigated.

Keywords: hydrogels, copolymers, maleic anhydride, cyclopropane-containing allyl ethers, polyethylene glycols, degree of swelling, parameters of the hydrogel mesh.

1. Introduction

The hydrogels are one of the most widely studied and used materials in practice. They have many useful properties, such as the ability to retain large quantity of water, to imitate living tissue and react to external stimuli, which makes them very attractive biomaterials. Due to the wide range of properties, the hydrogels began to be used in tissue engineering as drug carriers, in wound dressing materials and other biomedical devices [1-4].

The copolymers of maleic anhydride with various vinyl monomers, which are successfully used in tissue engineering as building frames for the cultivation of living tissue cells or in drug delivery systems and other physiologically active substances are very often serves as the main material for the preparation of the hydrogels [5-7]. It is reported about preparation of cross-linked materials on the basis of a copolymer of methyl vinyl ether and maleic anhydride Gantrez® AN-139, cross-linked with polyethylene glycol (PEG). For example, Singh et al. [8] have investigated the influence of PEG

with various molecular weights on the physical-chemical properties of hydrogels prepared from Gantrez® AN-139 and PEG. It has been revealed that by changing the degree of crosslinking of hydrogels (by varying the molecular weight of PEG), the drug delivery rate can be changed. In the work of Caló et al. [9] has been reported about preparation of the hydrogel on the basis of Gantrez® and poly(vinyl alcohol) with good antibacterial properties. In addition, the obtained hydrogels had good mechanical indices and high adhesion, which made them very suitable materials for wound dressing. MA copolymers are of interest primarily because they are multifunctional: the structure of the macromolecule includes anhydride links and other functional groups, which are reaction centers for post-polymerization conversions [10-12]. Usually, the copolymerization of vinyl ethers with maleic anhydride is accompanied by the appearance of donor-acceptor complexes, the polymerization of which leads to a strict alternation of the links of both comonomers in the macromolecule chain [13]. For the development of biomedical devices and drug

delivery systems, such strict alternation of links in the macromolecule plays an important role.

In this work, the polymer hydrogels on the basis of alternating copolymers of cyclopropane-containing allyl ethers with maleic anhydride cross-linked with polyethylene glycol PEG-300 have been obtained and their ability to swelling in an aqueous medium has been investigated.

2. Experimental Methods and Materials

Materials: Diallyl ether (pure for analysis), poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG, $M_n = 300$ Da), solvents: benzene (absolute), acetone, maleic anhydride (MA) were purified by recrystallization from chloroform. The initiator azo-*bis*-isobutyronitrile (AIBN) was used immediately after recrystallization from a solution of a mixture of chloroform and methanol at ratio of 1:5.

IR spectroscopy: The IR spectra of monomers, copolymers and hydrogels were taken on a "Cary 630 FTIR" spectrometer from Agilent Technologies (in the wave number range 600-4000 cm^{-1} , ZnSe crystal) with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

Thermogravimetry: The thermal stability of the copolymers was analyzed on derivatograph of mark Paulik-Paulik-Erdei. The samples (about 10 mg) were heated in an aluminum crucible from room temperature to 500°C at a rate of 10°C·min⁻¹, all measurements were carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere (10 ml/min).

Chromatographic investigations: The purity of the initial compounds and synthesized monomers was controlled by GLC method (liquid phase – Apiezon L (15%), KhE-60 (5%) and PEGA (5%); carriers – chromaton and zeolite-547; carrier gas – helium). The molecular weights of the copolymers were determined by gel-penetrating chromatography using styrogel columns as a standard.

Synthesis of monomers: The monomers were synthesized on well-known methods of cyclopropanation of the double bond by carbenes. The monomer 1 was obtained by addition of ethoxycarbonylcarbene formed by catalytic decomposition of ethyldiazoacetate in the presence of copper sulfate, the monomer 2 by addition of dichlorocarbene formed from chloroform under alkaline conditions in the presence of the catalyst of interphase transfer – TEBA-Cl (Makoshi method) on one of two double bonds of diallyl ether [14].

Synthesis of copolymers: The synthesis of copolymers was carried out in an ampoule in a benzene medium at 70°C in the presence of a radical initiator – AIBN, at an equimolar ratio of comonomers [15].

Synthesis of hydrogels: An acetone copolymer solution was made for the synthesis of hydrogels. The calculated quantity (per anhydride links) of polyethylene glycol as a crosslinking agent was added to the copolymer solution in acetone. The mixtures were placed in a round mold and left to react for 48 hours at room temperature and another 48 hours at 80°C.

Swelling Degree: The tests on the swelling ability of the hydrogels were carried out on samples with size 1×1 cm cut from preliminarily dried hydrogel films. The degree of swelling was determined gravimetrically by immersion of the samples in distilled water at room temperature and weighing them at time intervals. The

tests were completed on achievement of the equilibrium swelling of the samples. The calculations of the kinetic parameters of swelling and the parameters of the hydrogel mesh were carried out similar to the work [8].

The degree of swelling of the gel in % was calculated on **Formula 1**:

$$S = \frac{M_s - M_d}{M_d} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where

S – degree of swelling, %;

M_d – mass of the dried gel, g;

M_s – mass of the swollen gel in time τ , g.

The average swelling rate of the gels in water before the equilibrium state (\bar{v} , min⁻¹) was determined from the tangent of the angle of inclination of the direct dependence of the degree of swelling of the hydrogel on the time of its exposure in water. The coefficient of swelling rate ($k_{\bar{v}}$, min⁻¹) was calculated using the **Formula 2**:

$$k_{\bar{v}} = 1 / [\tau \cdot \ln(S_{eq} / (S_{eq} - S_{\tau}))] \quad (2)$$

where S_{eq} and S_{τ} – the degree of swelling of the gel at achievement of equilibrium and at time τ , respectively.

For study of the controlled mechanism of the swelling process of the hydrogels cross-linked with PEG, the treatment of the experimental data were carried out using **Equation 3** describing kinetic model of the second-order:

$$\frac{\tau}{S} = \frac{\tau}{S_{eq}} + \frac{\tau}{k_s S_{eq}^2} \quad (3)$$

For elucidation of the mechanism of water diffusion into the hydrogel matrix and for treatment of the kinetic data of the swelling process, the **Equation 4** was:

$$\frac{M_{\tau}}{M_{\infty}} = k\tau^n \quad (4)$$

where

M_{τ} – mass of water absorbed during the time τ ;

M_{∞} – water absorption at equilibrium;

k – constant taking into account the structure of the gel and its interaction with the solvent;

n – a swelling index describing the mechanism of solvent penetration into the gel matrix.

The average molecular weight value between the crosslinking was found by the Flory-Rener **Equation 5**:

$$M_{C_{eq}} = \frac{-d_p \cdot V_s \cdot \phi^{1/3}}{[\ln(1-\phi) + \phi + \chi \cdot \phi^2]} \quad (5)$$

The volume fraction of the polymer in the swollen state ϕ was determined using the **Equation 6**:

$$\phi = \left[1 + \frac{d_p}{d_s} \left(\frac{m_b}{m_a} \right) - \frac{d_p}{d_s} \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

where

V_s – molar volume of water ($V_s = 18 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$);

χ – is the Flory-Huggins polymer-solvent interaction parameter;

m_a and m_b – are the mass of polymer before and after swelling;

d_p and d_s – are the densities of polymer and solvent, respectively.

χ parameter of the interaction of the polymer with water was found on the basis of the results of experiments and calculated on the **Formula 7**:

$$\chi = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\phi}{3} \quad (7)$$

The crosslinking density value V_e was determined on the **Formula 8**:

$$V_e = d_p \cdot \frac{N_A}{M_C} \quad (8)$$

Where N_A – Avogadro number ($N_A = 6.023 \cdot 10^{23}$ mol⁻¹).

3. Results and Discussion

The linear macromolecules sewn into a three-dimensional network structure, at their placing in a solvent, in particular in water or a physiological liquid, are able to swell. This property strongly depends on the structural peculiarities of the macromolecule and the

crosslinking agent, their molecular weights, medium temperature, pH and ionic strength of the solution. In addition, the crosslinking density of the hydrogel also influences on the swelling rate. In this paper, we have investigated the influence of the structure of macromolecules of copolymers cross-linked with polyethylene glycol on the ability of the hydrogel to swelling in an aqueous medium.

For the synthesis of the hydrogel, the copolymers of maleic anhydride and cyclopropane-containing allyl ethers with ester and geminal chlorine substituents in the cyclopropane fragment were used. The cyclopropane-containing allyl ethers **1**, **2** have been synthesized on the scheme:

The IR spectroscopic investigations of monomers (**Figure 1**) showed the availability of cyclopropane fragments (1031 cm⁻¹), a double bond (1645 cm⁻¹), and also the availability of an ether (925, 1066, 1176 cm⁻¹)

bond. In the IR spectrum of compound **2** there is absorption band at 767 cm⁻¹ characteristics for chlorine atoms.

Figure 1. IR spectra of compounds **1** and **2**.

The synthesis of copolymers was carried out under the conditions of a free radical initiation reaction in a benzene medium with an equimolar ratio of comonomers.

The copolymers were weakly colored crystalline products, insoluble in aromatic hydrocarbons, well soluble in polar organic solvents. MW of copolymers found by the viscometric method (in a solution of THF at 20°C) were 5600-6800 g · mol⁻¹, respectively.

Thermal analysis of the copolymers showed that they are thermally stable up to 157°C. The loss of 5% of the mass of the MA copolymers with compounds **1** and **2** was observed at 155 and 147°C, respectively, and the loss of 50% of the mass of the copolymers was observed at 336 and 331°C, respectively.

The results of IR spectroscopy showed that the copolymerization of ethers with MA proceeded with the participation of a double bond with the formation of copolymers of linear structure and alternating structure. For increase of the hydrophilicity of the copolymers, they were subjected to hydrolysis, as a result of which the anhydride cycles were opened and the obtained copolymer had free carboxyl groups in its structure. For this purpose, the copolymer solutions were prepared in ice distilled water (0°C). For prevention of aggregation and complete wetting of the copolymer particles, the

mixtures were intensively mixed, heated and kept at 95–100°C for proceeding of the hydrolysis reaction, as evidenced by the transparency of the solution.

In **Figure 2** the IR spectra of copolymers: (a) – ethoxycarbonylcyclopropyl-methyl allyl ether and (b) – *gem*-dichlorocyclopropyl methyl allyl ether with maleic anhydride are presented.

Figure 2. IR spectra of copolymers: (a) – compound 1, (b) – compound 2 with maleic anhydride.

For preparation of the materials of the network structure, the copolymers were esterified with polyethylene glycol with a molecular weight of 300 Da at a ratio of 2:1. The esterification reaction between the carboxyl groups of anhydride cycles and the hydroxyl groups of PEG proceeded according to the scheme shown below.

Scheme of hydrogel synthesis by copolymer esterification reaction PEG-300.

It is noteworthy that during this reaction, the cyclopropane fragments located in the chain of the macromolecule of copolymers remain untouched. As is known, the cyclopropane group is a key component of many drugs, and the introduction of new drugs of the cyclopropane group into the structure can give them new specific pharmacological properties [16]. It was also important for us to preserve the cyclopropane fragments in the structure of the cross-linked polymer.

The esterification reaction between the carboxyl groups of anhydride cycles and the hydroxyl groups of

PEG was judged by the IR spectra of the obtained hydrogels. In the IR spectrum of the esterified samples, the disappearance of bands at 1852 cm^{-1} and 1776 cm^{-1} characteristic for anhydride fragments and the appearance of a strong band $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of the ester and bands characteristic for free COON -groups at 1702, 2680 and 2602 cm^{-1} , was observed respectively (**Figure 3**). In the spectra of samples, it can also be observed the bands at 1040 cm^{-1} characteristic for the cyclopropane group.

Figure 3. IR spectrum of cross-linked PEG copolymer of compound 1.

The obtained resin-like adhesive products for proceeding of the esterification reaction were subjected to chemical crosslinking at 80°C for 48 h. The esterified copolymers were transparent, elastic, films painted in intensive yellow color (due to the solvatochromic properties of the copolymers [17]) with sufficiently good adhesion to the glass substrate (**Figure 4**).

Copolymer hydrogel of compound 1

Copolymer hydrogel of compound 2

Figure 4. The appearance of thermally cross-linked PEG-300 copolymers.

The ability of cross-linked materials to swell in water or physiological solutions is an important property if they will be used as carriers of biologically active compounds. The hydrogels formed from comonomers with high hydrophobicity or volume substituents creating steric difficulties have a reduced ability to absorb water. On the other hand, the ability to swell can be ad-

justed by changing the degree of crosslinking of the hydrogel by selection of the ratio of the copolymer and the crosslinking agent or the type of crosslinking agent and its molecular weight. The hydrogels obtained by us have been tested for the ability to swelling for 300 h in distilled water at room temperature. According to the test results, the swelling curves have been constructed (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Dependence of the degree of swelling on the time of the hydrogel obtained from: 1 – copolymer of compound 1 with maleic anhydride; 2 – copolymer of compound 1 with maleic acid.

The equilibrium swelling of the hydrogels of the copolymer of compound 1 and its hydrolyzed analog under the studied conditions (at 25°C, pH = 7) was 66 and 71%, respectively. The degrees of swelling have been calculated on the Formula 1.

The average swelling rate of gels in water before the equilibrium state (\bar{v} , min^{-1}) was determined as the tangent of the angle of inclination depending on the degree of swelling of the hydrogel on the keeping time in water. The hydrogel swelling rate constant was calculated on the Formula 2. It can be seen from the obtained

calculations that k_v value practically is not changed in a neutral medium.

For study of the controlled mechanism of hydrogel swelling, the Equation 3 describing kinetic model of the

second-order was used for treatment of the experimental data. From the graphs of linear regression of swelling (Figure 6), on the basis of the dependence of t/S on τ , the pseudo-second-order swelling rate constants were found.

Figure 6. Dependence of t/S on τ time of linear regression of swelling.

For elucidation the mechanism of water diffusion into the hydrogel and treatment of the kinetic data of the swelling process, the Formula 4 was used. After logarithm of Equation 4, a graph of the dependence of $\ln(M_t/M_\infty)$ on $\ln \tau$ was plotted, and n and k values were graphically determined. $n < 0.5$ values found in this way indicate the diffusion mechanism of hydrogel swelling. In Table the results of kinetic calculations and the parameters of the hydrogel mesh on the basis of ethoxycarbonyl substituted cyclopropylmethylallyl ether

with maleic anhydride (1) and its hydrolyzed analog (2) are presented.

As is known, the swelling of polymer meshes of hydrogels has been connected with a change of their structure. The possibility of their use as drug carriers depends on parameters such as the density of crosslinks, the average molecular weight between crosslinks or the volume fraction of the polymer in the swollen state. These characteristics of the mesh parameters determine their usefulness and potential area of their application [18,19].

Table.

Some kinetic characteristics and parameters of the hydrogels mesh on the basis of copolymer 1 and its hydrolyzed analog (2).

Hydrogel	S, %	$k_0 \times 10^{-5}$ (g gel/ gH ₂ O)/min	r_0 , (gH ₂ O/ g gel)/min	n	$k \times 10^{-2}$	ϕ	Mc (eq) g/mol ⁻¹	χ	$V_e \times 10^{20}$
1	66	20.06	3.3	0.41	2.12	0.94	664	0.813	12.85
2	71	22.16	3.5	0.43	2.37	0.92	765	0.807	11.09

The volume fraction of the polymer in the swollen state, calculated by formula (6), shows how much liquid can be absorbed into the hydrogel matrix. These values, as can be seen from the data in the Table, indicate the formation of a sufficiently dense polymer mesh. The average calculated molecular weights between the crosslinking, calculated by the Flory-Rener Equation 5, take into account the availability of free movement of the polymer chain between adjacent crosslinking in a hydrogel swollen in a solvent. In the obtained hydrogels, the molecular weights between the crosslinking have low values. On the contrary, the high crosslinking density values (V_e) per unit volume of hydrogel in the swollen state also indicate a tightly cross-linked network structure of the obtained hydrogels. Such mesh materials, as a rule exhibit a low swelling rate. On the other hand, the influence of the structural parameters of the copolymers forming the hydrogel mesh is also obvious. The relatively large volume of substituent with cyclopropane group, showing a hydrophobic character, also prevents the penetration of a large quantity of water into the hydrogel matrix.

Nevertheless, the obtained materials can be used in such systems controlled delivery of medicinal compounds, where a high rate of their release is not required. The preliminary tests showed that in a medium with $\text{pH} \approx 9$, these materials show greater swelling than in a neutral medium. Therefore, our further investigations will be aimed at studying the swelling process of these hydrogels depending on pH medium and temperature.

4. Conclusion

The polymer hydrogels on the basis of alternating copolymers of cyclopropane-containing allyl ethers cross-linked with polyethylene glycol have been synthesized, the kinetics of their swelling in water has been investigated and the parameters of the hydrogel mesh have been calculated. The behavior of the obtained hydrogels during swelling in water has been shown. The maximum equilibrium swelling of these hydrogels in distilled water did not exceed 71%. The calculated values of the mesh parameters show that the obtained materials are tightly cross-linked meshes with small free volume for solvent diffusion into the cell, which has

been probably caused not only by the ratio of the copolymer and the crosslinking agent, but also by the structural peculiarities of the used copolymers. The practical application of these materials is possible in the systems with delayed release of drugs, and the high adhesion predetermines their possible use as components of membranes and other devices.

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